

Validation of the suitability for bioplastics production and uses as packaging material-First Version

Deliverable 6.5

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Lead Partner: ITENE

Contributor(s): WETSUS

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

This WP proposes a “start to end” valorisation process of the urban sewage sludge (USS) and organic fraction from municipal solid waste (OFMSW) to obtain ready-to-use products. Different processes will be studied to demonstrate the feasibility to obtain high-value products from raw biowastes (OFMSW and USS). These processes will be validated in prototypes operated in three demonstration sites: DS 1 (ES), DS6 (CZ) and DS7 (NL). Special attention will be given to the key operation parameters and system design for the production of target valuable end-products to be adapted at DSs.

At DS7 (The Netherlands), a pilot application of the PHARIO technology is being developed for PHA (Polyhydroxyalkanoates) production from municipal surplus secondary activated sludge and fermented organic waste. PHA are biodegradable thermoplastics with the potential to replace fossil fuel based polymers.

Deliverable 6.5 aims to describe the full characterization of the PHA produced by Wetsus. To validate their processability, ITENE will process the biopolymers by means of pilot extrusion and/or injection equipment in function of their properties to obtain blow films and/or rigid packages such as cups of the different formulations produced by Wetsus. In addition, the compliance with the Framework Regulation (EC) No. 1935/2004 on materials and articles to come into contact with food will be demonstrated for the new packaging materials

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